

**CAMBRIDGE'S MODEL FOR THE FORMATION OF TEACHER'S INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE
UPDATED CONTENT OF EDUCATION IN KAZAKHSTAN**

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Abstract

This study aims to confirm the effectiveness of practical application of the Cambridge model of formation of teacher's innovative activity in the context of the updated content of education in Kazakhstan. This model poses a three-level training program to change mindset, professional understanding, competence and practical teaching skills. The research is presented on the basis of the theoretical analysis of modern domestic and foreign scientific literature on this topic, generalization of psychological and pedagogical research in the field of innovative pedagogical activity. Within the framework of this research was applied a set of methods (testing, questioning, observation, conversation), mathematical and statistical methods data processing, allowing to assess the impact this program on teacher's innovative activity through practical application of the Cambridge model. The completeness and reliability of the data obtained in the course of research work was ensured using the methods of mathematical statistics.

The main results of the study are to prove the effectiveness of the implementation of Cambridge's model that contribute to the expansion of teacher's methodological arsenal, increasing his professional competence, which based on the competence of personal self-development. The introduction of the theoretical model created by us into a educational process has made it possible to increase the level of the motivational, projective components of teacher's innovative activity. It's reflected in the productive nature of the educational students' achievements and activation of cognitive activity.

Keywords: innovation; teacher's innovative activity, professional competence; updating of educational content; quality of learning; new approaches; cognitive activity.

Introduction

Appeal to the problem of the formation of teacher's innovative activity in the context of updating the content of education is dictated by changes in the global economy, which have given rise to the need to adapt to a more competitive economic environment, where the problems of the quality of education and the development of human index have become especially actual.

The interest to the problem is due to the fact that the world of the 21st century forms new demands for the quality and development of the competencies of the workforce, therefore. the education system needs to adapt to the needs of the economy in the context of development of advanced technology and market transformations. To ensure the dynamics of increasing the growth of human index and economic growth, the educational system needs to develop new approaches to training persons, taking into account their level of knowledge, skills and development paths.

In the State Program for the Development of Education and Sciences of Kazakhstan for 2011-2020 takes into account one of the four trends in the world education, namely, the high teacher's qualification (Elorda. 2017).

The relevance of the study of this problem is due to the fact that updating the content of education is impossible without teacher's professional self-improvement and competencies. Its ability to innovate in the VUCA world becomes a decisive condition for the country's competitive advantage.

According to Andreas Schleicher, special adviser to the OECD Secretary General on Education Policy, the 21st century's schools must prepare students to live and work in the world, where most people need to cooperate with people of different cultures, take into account different ideas, perspectives and values (Schleicher A 2015).

Since September 2016, schools in Kazakhstan have transferred to the updated content of education. In 2012-2015 years has been successfully implemented a three-level program for the further teachers' training to change mindset, professional understanding, practical teaching skills, developed by "Nazarbayev Intellectual Schools" in cooperation with the Faculty of Education of Cambridge University. Strategic Partner, University of Cambridge (UK is the world's largest internationally renowned and world-renowned scholar.

The content of the program was consistent with the Objectives of the Strategy for the Development of Kazakh Education and the recommendations of

UNESCO and OECD. The updated syllabus of the courses is adapted to the specific subject matter and allows teachers to apply the knowledge and skills acquired in the course more effectively.

Источник: НЦПК «Өрлеу», АОО НИШ

Diagram 1 a number of participants of three-level program

In 2012-2015. were trained 52,885 teachers under the level programs, 36,173 teachers under the program of the third (basic)level, 7,647 teachers of the second (basic) level, 9,065 teachers of the first (advanced) level. This is the critical mass of teachers, which was to introduce new pedagogical technologies into the updated content of education (National report,2017).

According to this program, teachers of the third (basic line) level implement the ideas of the seven modules within the classroom. Second (basic) level teachers

implement ideas not only in the classroom, but also at school level. Teachers of the first (advanced) level implement changes not also at school, but also in the network professional interaction. An innovative aspect of this model is a level approach to learning. The level-based approach involved a change in thinking, working methods and tools(NIS, 2014)

Table 1.

School development promotion factors.

Key factors	Teacher's Leadership in classroom	Teacher's Leadership in School	Teacher's Leadership in School and school networks
	Third (basic line) level	Second (basic) level	Level 1(advanced)
Mindset	How do we learn? Learning to think critically. Identifying talented and gifted students	Learning how to learn Teamwork in groups	Networking and networking School Development planning
Methods of work	Methods of Work Dialogue learning Reflections on the practice	Coaching and mentoring Lesson Study Action Research	Leadership at school Network Professional Associations
Tools for the work	Peer review and self-evolution Medium-term planning (series of incremental lessons) and evolution.	Plans for coaching and mentoring processes. Action planning	School Development Planning Research practice

Literature Review

It's known fact, the quality of professional services to a large extent depends on the teacher's professional training and qualification, therefore " updating the content of secondary education is impossible without the professional development of teaching staff (Barber, M., Murshead, M. 2008). Improving the quality of school teaching staff is more urgent today than ever, as global threats are threefold projected into the teaching profession, and update the content of secondary education is impossible without the professional development of teaching staff. The competitiveness of the future

teacher is determined by the high demands of the developing labour market.

The quality of educational services depends to a large extent on the vocational training and teacher's qualifications and consequently the content of secondary education cannot be renewed without the professional development of teaching staff (Ruddock1995).

The updating of the content of education is, first of all, the revision of the model of secondary education itself, its structure, content, approaches and methods of education and upbringing, the introduction of a fundamentally new system of evaluation of the achievement

of pupils in the system of relationships “teacher – pupil”. The whole range of measures taken to update the content of education is aimed at creating an educational environment conducive to the harmonious development and development of the individual.

The results of the renewal of the content of education should be that the educational achievements will be productive, and the actual learning process will be characterized by the active students' activity themselves in “obtaining” knowledge at each lesson. In these conditions, “...the student is the subject of his knowledge”.

The central figure of the educational process and its cognitive activities are the focus of the educational researchers (Barber, and Murshead 2008). To solve problems, where “...emphasis in education is shifted towards the “4c” model - development of creativity, critical thinking communication and cooperation skills”(Elorda 2017).

In pedagogical science, innovative activity is understood as a purposeful activity based on reflection of own practical experience by comparing and studying, changing and developing the educational process in order to achieve better results, obtain new knowledge and a qualitatively different pedagogical practice. The development of a person's motivational sphere, instilling the habit of systematic work on the development of own human index, the focus of achieving acme in socially significant activities are the main task facing the education system today

The issues of a teacher's professional development are reflected in the studies of Kazakh scientists Zhaitapova A.A., Taubaeva Sh.T., Karaev Zh.A., Kobdikova Zh.U., Islamgulova S.K., Zhanpeisova M.M., Kolumbaeva Sh. Zh.. For example, according to Sh. T. Taubaeva, modern transformations of the school and society require a teacher to reorient his activities to new pedagogical values that are adequate to the nature of research activities, creative understanding of pedagogical reality (Taubaeva Sh, 2001)

The professional development of A. Zhaitapova is considered as a process of change, transformation of pedagogical activity, leading to sustainable development of professionalism, based on competence of personal development. The author distinguishes three levels of professional development: level of change, level of transformation, level of sustainable development. The innovative performance of a teacher is an indicator of the development of his professional competence, where professional self-knowledge leads to a teacher's need for professional self-improvement (Zhaitapova 2006). According to Professor Kolymbayeva S., teacher's professional self-improvement is a conscious, purposeful process of increasing his professional competence, developing professional qualities in accordance with external social requirements, pedagogical and personal development's program (Kolumbaeva 2016).

The scientific and pedagogical literature of Russian scientists reflects various areas of research into innovative activities such as general and specific features of this activity. From the point of view of studying pedagogical achievements and disseminating best practices, the teacher's innovative activity is studied by

Slastenin V.A., Podymova L.S., Polyakov S.D., Lazarev V.S. and Martirosyan B.P.. Features of innovative phenomena of the modern education system are considered by Yusufbekova N.R., Burgin M.S., Klarin V., Zagvyazinsky V.I.

R.N. Yusufbekova identifies three blocks in the innovative structure of pedagogical activity

-1 block- the creation of a new one in the methodology of pedagogy, which considers the system of concepts "new" in the classification of innovations, conditions and criteria, stages of creating a new one:

- 2 block- block of perception, development and evaluation of the new, community environment, value of the new:

-3 block- use, application of the new, introduction of pedagogical innovation (Yusufbekova N.R, 2010)

According to the definition of V.S. Lazarev and B.P. Martirosyan, innovative activity is understood as the introduction of innovations into the pedagogical system in order to improve the quality of education (Lazarev V.S, 2007)

From the point of view of V.I. Zagvyazinsky, “..” innovation contains only a progressive beginning, it is not only ideas, approaches, methods, technologies, but also a complex of elements or individual elements of the pedagogical process that carry a progressive beginning, which allows in changing conditions and situations to effectively solve the problems of bringing and education (Zagvyazinsky V.I., 2011)

We agree with opinion of Novikova G.P. that the school's development is determined by “... the productivity of teachers' innovative activities in solving the problems of improving educational activities, targeted changes in the school's pedagogical system, leading to an increase its efficiency (Novikova G.P. 2016).

Innovation is understood as a realized change in any area of social development aimed at obtaining a positive effect, which is expressed in the form of competitive advantages of the object of the ongoing changes (Alexeeva, I. 2017).

A significant contribution to pedagogical innovation was made by L.S. Podymova and L.S. Slastenin in the study of “innovation” as “... a telic change introduced into a certain social unit- an organization, a settlement, a society a group- new, relatively, stable elements” (Slastenin, V., Podymova, L. 1997).

Lazarev V.S updates that “... the main characteristics of innovative activity are its efficiency and effectiveness” (Lazarev V.S. 2011).

Consequently, innovation activity is a complex of scientific, technical, organizational actions aimed at creating, using innovations by introducing them into the educational process.

The results itself appears in the form of improved research methods, new results obtained creation of new products, principles (Sergienko Yu.A., 2016).

Innovative activity must have a personal meaning, where the motive coincides with the demands of society, defining the goal, taking responsibility for the implementation of innovative activities, choosing methods and means for implementing innovative activities, evaluating the results, mastering the cultural methods of its implementation (Lazarev V.S., 2009).

A professional motive combined with a high level of creativity ensures optimal impact. Such teachers are characterized by the search for innovative forms and methods of work, understanding their activities, creating their own concept of teaching and educating children.

A characteristic feature of professional motivation is the focus of innovation on the student. Answering the question "What motivates you to innovate in the pedagogical process?", teachers with professional motivation gave the following answers:

- striving for more stimulation of children (38%);
- the desire to achieve better assimilation of knowledge and skills by students (39%);
- the desire to develop the creative abilities of students (23%)

The motives of self-realization occupy a rather high place in the system of motives for the teacher's innovative activity, they were noted by 27% of teachers (Slastenin, V., Podymova, L. 1997)

The teacher is an organizer of the students' cognitive activity. Respectively solve problems and tasks where "... the emphasis in education is shifting towards the 4C model- the development of creativity, critical thinking, communication skills, the ability to work in a team (Elorda. 2017).

According to Shulman's theory, quality teaching can be presented as a symbiosis of learners, the environment and the conditions for teaching and learning. The characteristics of a successful teacher are professional understanding, practical teaching skills, professional and moral integrity. In order to translate change into school development, we will focus on key factors in level program (Shulman 2007).

Foreign researchers understand the teacher's development a competence as the development of the teacher's creative personality, the preparation for the adoption of a new one, the development of receptivity to pedagogical innovations. The pedagogical competence of a teacher is a continuous process which is constantly evaluated through interaction with colleagues, students (Kunter, and Klustman 2013).

The studies of H.Elrehail, O.E.Emeagwali, A.Asaad, A.Alzghout consider innovations that require major changes in the organization, where the transformational management style is the most effective in the promoting innovations (Elrehail H. 2018)

The analysis of scientific research by R. Khatri, C. Henderson, R. Cole, D. Friedrichsen, C. Stanford allows to study the problem of adoption of scientifically based educational innovations. According to scientists, long-term thinking is relevant for the widespread introduction of new pedagogical innovations (Khatri, Henderson, Cole, Froyd, Friedrichsen, and Stanford 2017).

According to E.M.Sutanto, the creation of a creative environment, an atmosphere of universal desire for learning, development will lead to the emergence of new ideas. Leaders must demonstrate a strategy of cooperation, expansion of freedom, which creates a favorable climate (Sutanto E. M.2017) F.Guay allows us to consider a conceptual model based on the theory of

self-determination in order to study the motivation (external and internal) of teachers to use advanced technologies in practice (F.Guay 2018)

The study of M.G.M. Koeslag- Kreunen, Marcel R.Van der Klink, Van den Bossche Piet, Gijsselaers Wim H. showed that teachers prefer to work in an atmosphere of exchange of ideas, experience and knowledge. They expect management not to control, but to cooperate (Koeslag-Kreunen M.G.M.2018)

Kauffman D, U.Diaz-Orueta, Y.Kauffman believe that introduction of innovations has become a challenge for the professional academic environment, as it has led to the emergence of completely new qualification requirements (Kauffman D.2018).

C.L.Weitze considers the problem of creating conditions in the teaching staff for successful innovation (Weitze C. L.2018) Theoretical analysis of research of R.H.Stupnisky, A.BrckaLorenz, B.Yuha,F.Guay allows us to consider a conceptual model based on the theory of self-determination in order to study the teachers' motivation (external and internal) to use advanced technologies in practice (R.H.Stupnisky, A.BrckaLorenz, B.Yuha,F.Guay 2018)

One of the leaders of the world's education rating, Singapore, offers 5 desired qualities to a teacher of the 21st century; an ethical educator, a competent and cooperative professional, a transformational leader, and an active participant in community development (Almukhambetov 2018).

Methods and methodology

An examination of the current experience of the teacher's willingness to innovate, the content analysis of publications on the relevant problem in the academic circles of domestic and foreign scientists led to the conclusion that the study requires the use of a psychodiagnostic complex, which can measure the impact of new approaches on the productivity of innovation by teachers in meeting the challenges of improving the educational process. The main method of this research was a set of methods of scientific and pedagogical research, observation and questionnaire to detect changes in the development of teacher's professional competence and its readiness to innovative activities.

The pedagogical experiment took place at the secondary school 14 in Kokshetau from 2017 to 2020. Our conceptual empirical research consisted of the following phases: At the ascertaining stage, students of 7 grades participated as a pilot experimental group (EEG), students of 6 grades as a control group (CG)

The diagnosis of the initial and achieved level of the components, indicators of innovation the teachers' competence of the experimental and control groups was confirmed by the use

- Teacher's Sensitivity to the New NIS Diagnostic Collection' to identify the motivational component;
- 'Diagnostic map of success' (according to I.V.Nikishina) for definition of projective component.

The validation of the obtained data from the results of the research was tested by mathematical statistics using t-scientific Student criterion.

The pilot group was conducted using new approaches of Cambridge three-level program, active and

interactive learning methods. Lesson Study brought together groups of teachers who jointly plan, teach, observe, analyze learning and teaching, documenting their findings. According to Dudley Pete, this approach allows teachers to be more aware and take into account the needs of each student throughout their practice, while not “overloading” their experience with secondary information (Dudley, P. (2011).

In order to enhance professional competencies, a culture of teachers' professional development was held coach sessions, master classes, which helped to deepen understanding of key ideas of the Cambridge program “New Approaches in Learning”.

Correct SMART setting of lesson goals, evaluation methodology, lesson performance criteria, theoretical and practical knowledge helped teachers to transform teaching style in the light of new approaches to the updated content of education.

Mentors took an active part in the teachers' professional development as the attitudes and the teacher's style of work will change when immersed in an environment corresponding to the direction of change. A change in a teacher’s attitude and work style takes place in a collaborative environment, corresponding to the direction of changes in his thinking, teaching style and expansion of his methodological arsenal.

Results and Data Analysis

The positive impact of the practical implementation of the new approaches of Cambridge three-level training program has been empirically confirmed .on the learning motivation of students Innovative pedagogical approaches to productive thinking are shaped by self-mainstreaming.

Within the framework of our study, the most relevant and reliable indicators will be considered:-

-Motivational component (self-assessment, professional self-realization, openness and personal relevance of innovation) according to the collection of NIS diagnostics:(Teacher’s Sensitivity to the New NIS Diagnostic Collection,2014)

-Projective component (ability to organise a pedagogical experiment, ability to create a concept of innovation) according to diagnostics map of Nikishina I.V (Diagnostic map of success” (according to I.V.Nikishina,2012)

In analyzing the empirical data from the teachers' tests, we used as statistical methods the calculation of the Student's t-criterion for 6 pairs and 2 independent samples as a means of assessing their validity and relevance.

At the first stage of the analytical work, empirical values of the Scientific criterion were calculated (table 2).

Table 2.

Empirical values of the Student Criterion.

Scale names	Mean value in the control group		Mean value in the pilot group	
	before	after	before	after
Motivational	8.45±0.887	10.7±0.865	7.5±0.607	23.2±1.196
Projective	29.3±1.031	37.55±1.986	37.55±1.986	57.6±1.231

The interpretation of the data showed a level of importance p = 0.024, which in the given study p 0.05 can lead to a conclusion on the statistical reliability of the results of the teacher testing to confirm the experimental hypothesis. In the second step, the zero hypothesis we test for normally distributed general populations with equal median values determined the t-criterion formula as follows:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{S_{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}} \tag{1}$$

where standard denominator error:

$$S_{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2} = \sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}} \tag{2}$$

On the basis of two independent samples of control group and experimental group, calculation of t-criterion where S₁ and S₂ are sample variance estimates has been carried out. Thus, at t = 2.024c the number of degrees of freedom f = 38, the resulting coefficient of p = 0.001621 indicates the statistical significance of the measurement of these populations Without taking into account the zero hypothesis of the equality of data averages, the probability of obtaining an erroneous result is about 0.1%. The true error, with a probability of 95%, is in the range 2.5 to -1.0

Figure 1. Average indicators of the motivational component of teacher’s innovative activity

Figure 2. Average indicators of the projective component of teacher's innovative activity

We have evaluated the evolution of the teachers' professional development in the pilot group according to two criteria: competence in personal development and technological skill.

Indicators such as noted the level of satisfaction of the teachers' pilot team:

- Increasing motivation to learn from pupils;
- Lessons learned using program modules;
- An opportunity for experimentation in class;
- A positive development in pupils' achievements;
- Increasing motivation to teach.

Figure 3. Educational satisfaction of the teachers' pilot group

Discussion

We have considered that the teachers of pilot group are qualified on the level of heuristic innovation. It is generally characterized by greater focus, sustainability, awareness of the ways and means of innovation. Significant changes are taking place in the structure of the technological component, which reflects the development of the personality of the teacher as the subject of an alternative concept, technology or content of education. With a fairly reliable technology, the teacher continues to seek and discover new ways of pedagogical solutions

The results of the implementation of key ideas of level programs are most obvious in such indicators as

- a positive psychological climate in the classroom;
- motivation for learning;
- opportunities for professional growth and teacher's professional self-realization;
- expanding the methodological arsenal with new competencies

Conclusion

The conducted research proved the didactic value of practical application this program on the learning

motivation in the context of teacher's innovative activity It has been established that the implementation methodically accessible and has a positive effect on the motivational sphere of both teachers and students, which affects the effectiveness of the educational process. Teaching methodology and evaluation is one of the most important principles of the updated educational programs, contributing both to the student's progress and to the teacher's methodological excellence.

The introduction of the theoretical model, created into the whole educational process has made it possible to increase the level of motivational, projective components of teachers' innovative activity. Positive changes in the teaching practices of the teachers' pilot group through changes in the way of thinking, working methods and working tools have had a positive impact on the motivational aspects of the activities of both pupils and teachers.

The use of active and interactive methods, Lesson Study influenced the increase of motivation, the satisfaction of professional competences. According to the teachers' of pilot group, the lack of readiness to manage and correct innovative activity was one of the most difficult tasks.

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